

HYATT
PUNE

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April 18, 2022

TO WHOM SO EVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to inform you that **Ms. K. Ashritha** has undergone her **Internship** at **Hyatt Pune, Kalyani Nagar** from **December 20, 2021 to April 18, 2022** as a part of her curriculum at **Srinivas University, College of Hotel Management And Tourism, Mangalore**. She had done her internship in Food & Beverage, Front Office, Housekeeping and Culinary with **100%** attendance during the prescribed internship period.

During this time, she was found to be very sincere and hardworking.

We wish her all the best in her future endeavors.

For Hyatt Pune,

Nitin Shevde
Human Resource Manager

